

TARTYP GENERATIVE GRAMMARS AND THE ANALYSIS OF HIP HOP BEATS

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ABSTRACT

Pierre Schaeffer's *musique concrete* is considered to be the predecessor of digital sampling. The latter is a defining element in the development of hip hop. Drawing on historic and stylistic connections between these genres, we suggest the use of the Schaefferian core typology, the TARTYP, in the analysis of hip hop beats. We present a TARTYP classification of the beat's basic components, based on samples taken from the pre-mastered multitrack sessions of professionally produced hip hop songs, mapping these components to TARTYP sound object types. We use this classification to define sets of rewrite rules in the TARTYP generative grammars that we have presented in previous studies. We demonstrate how a path extracted from a rewrite rule set within the TARTYP Balanced grammar regenerates a representative hip hop drum pattern.

1. INTRODUCTION

The connection between hip hop music and Pierre Schaeffer's *musique concrete* is usually drawn from a technical perspective. *Musique concrete* is considered to be the predecessor of digital sampling. The latter is a defining element in the stylistic development of hip hop. In a historical review of sampling techniques Howell maintains that the precursors of the digital sampling method introduced by the Fairlight CMI in the 1970s were the sampling techniques used by Pierre Schaeffer in his *musique concrete* [1]. A similar idea was expressed by Tully in [2]:

Sampling is the digital equivalent of music concrete, wherein common sounds are manipulated (and sometimes integrated with traditional instruments) to produce musical compositions.

While Tully and Howell are concerned with digital sampling as a technology, Schloss, in [3], sees it as a hip hop aesthetic, an underlying principle of this musical genre. However, is the connection between these two genres based only on technological developments or are there any aesthetic connections that can be made between *musique concrete* and hip hop?

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Along with the introduction of *musique concrete*, Pierre Schaeffer presented a theoretical body of work known as Schaefferian theory. To this day this is the most significant theoretical work on electronic music. Theoretical analysis of hip hop music is scarce. Adams writes about hip hop that it "resists traditional modes of musical analysis more than any other genre" [4]. In one of the main studies of rap music [5], Krims uses the term "music poetics" as a substitution for music theory to stress the need for an analytical method that takes in to account the text, the music and the cultural and social context by which they were created, as well as their creators. Krims analyzes the synchronization of the text with 16-points subdivision of the bar [5]. Studies by Sewell and Boone have suggested typologies as methods for hip hop analysis. Sewell focuses on the compositional functions of samples in sample-based hip-hop songs [6]. Boone presents a typology of works in popular music that are using sampled material [7]. In the following pages we are going to draw on technical and esthetical connections between *musique concrete* and hip hop, and suggest the use of the core typology of Schaefferian theory, the TARTYP, coupled with the TARTYP generative grammars [8, 9] as a method for analyzing hip hop beats.

2. BACKGROUND

A comparison between hip hop and *musique concrete* is based on the fact that both genres are using recorded sound as source material in the compositional process. This is in contrast to using sound recording to capture a performance or a realization of a composition that otherwise exists as an abstract idea expressed in symbolic notation. In regard to hip hop Adams says:

In hip-hop, the sound object and the composition are one: songs exist as recordings, rarely transcribed into musical notation and even more rarely performed from musical notation [4].

The term sound object is fundamental to Schaefferian theory. Chion defines the sound object as follows:

The name sound object refers to every sound phenomenon and event perceived as a whole, a coherent entity, and heard by means of reduced listening, which targets it for itself, independently of its origin or its meaning [10].

He continues to say that the "sound object is not a notated symbol on a score" [10]. Both genres gravitate towards the specifics of sound and away from its abstraction and symbolic representation. While Chion also says that "the sound object is not a recorded fragment" [10] because a recorded fragment can be processed to sound in different ways, it is

clear that in both genres recoding techniques are the main tools for defining and fixing the identity of sound objects.

Differences between *musique concrete* and hip hop are found in artistic choices, starting with choices of sound sources. As demonstrated in [11], *musique concrete* considers a wide array of sound sources including studio recordings of traditional acoustic instruments, studio recordings of non-traditional acoustic instruments and techniques such as prepared piano and extended techniques, sound generated by found objects, sound captured in different environments (soundscapes), and electronically generated sound. In the hip-hop golden era of the 1980s and 1990s, sampling was done primarily from existing recordings of popular music in the format of analog LPs (vinyl records) [3]. These recordings were mainly of conventional instruments (acoustic and electric) playing tonal harmonies and melodies. However, their use in hip hop productions was much less conventional. Scratching and turntablism, focusing on the sampling of percussive sounds, introduced noise elements. The blurring of the bass by boosting sub-sonic frequencies, along with the cyclic nature of the music reduced its functionality in the tonal environment.

Starting with DJ Kool Herc in the early 1980s, the practice of sampling was focused on creating “breaks” with excerpts from well-known songs that could be recognized by the audience. Schloss describes the evolution of the deejay’s approach to breaks as moving away from the recognizable songs towards the producer’s “unique selections.” While a canon of recordings suited for breaks was developed and was a prerequisite for hip hop producers, many producers built their reputation based on their ability to find rare recordings to sample their breaks from. Many producers rejected resources such as the Ultimate Breaks and Beats collections to maintain their original choices of sampling [3]. This focus on rare recordings for sampling breaks emphasized the importance of the break itself and how it sounds while diminishing the importance of the source and the audience ability to recognize the original song.

The treatment of the break as a coherent entity, independent of its sampled source, goes even deeper into the hip hop compositional and production process. Through interviews with producers Prince Paul and Jake One, Schloss shows how the unique and concrete characteristics of the sample influence and guide the hip hop producer’s compositional choices. Prince Paul maintains that consistency of texture plays an important role in the selection of samples he uses in his beats. Schloss in turn sees Prince Paul’s approach as “an aesthetic that is more concerned with a cohesive organizing principle than the diversity of individual elements that fall into its orbit” [3]. He further argues, based on a 1998 interview with Jake One, that hip hop production prefers sampling over live instruments because the very specific (i.e., concrete) character of the sample provides the producer better “musical clues” into the compositional process. In contrast, live instruments, according to Jake One, “could play anything” [3], i.e., interpretations of symbolic music notation performed by a live musician could yield a number of actual sound recordings of which the producer has little control over.

The ideas expressed by hip hop producers, which were discussed so far, are comparable with some of the fundamental concepts of Schaefferian theory and *musique concrete*. Both genres have emerged from the latest innovations of the day, primarily technological innovations, and in spite of strong resistance from established musical genres. Schaeffer writes about *musique concrete*:

We will look at how we introduce a new element, a present-day invention, in fact, into a somewhat fossilized musical heritage that is, however, nothing other than the summation of successive inventions, going back through history, a whole evolution of musical concepts, always related to the means available to music [12].

Furthermore, two of the basic ideas guiding Schaeffer’s concept of reduced listening are also expressed by hip hop producers in the above passages. In reduced listening, the sound object is targeted “for itself independently of its origin or its meaning” [10]. This is similar to deejays realizing that the recognizability of the sampled source is insignificant to the quality of the break. The hearing of the sound object as a coherent unit is tied in Schaefferian theory with identifying the object’s sound characteristics as demonstrated by Schaeffer’s focus on typology and the TARTYP in particular. Again, a parallel idea is expressed by hip hop producers acknowledging that the sound characteristics of the sample inform the compositional process.

This last comparison is reinforced by both genres’ similar approach to music notation. As Adams maintains, hip hop producers do not use music notation [4]. Chion claims that “the sound object is not a notated symbol on a score” [10]. The Schaefferian rejection of music notation emerged as resistance to a contextual environment in which the composition’s existence is first and foremost on the page as music notation. The genres preceding hip hop, such as blues and jazz, already had substantial part of the music done without music notation. But hip hop takes the same principle further to resist also the use of live instruments. As Jake One explains in the interview with Schloss, live instruments “could play anything” [3], i.e., we cannot predict how the performance will sound. The sound object and sampled break on the other hand are concrete recordings with defined characteristics and specific audibility.

3. BEAT CLASSIFICATION

The discussion in this section will focus on the “beat”, i.e., the instrumental tracks that accompany the vocals in the hip hop song. These instrumental tracks are usually produced by a combination of tools and techniques including sampling, software instruments, synthesis and to lesser extent live instruments. The hip hop esthetics perceive the song production as a dichotomy of the vocals and the beat. These two entities are usually distinguished by creators as the hip hop artist is responsible for the vocals and the hip hop producer is responsible for the beat. Furthermore, the vocals and the beat may undergo independent creative processes. The artist would many times create the flow (i.e., lyrics) on a pre-existing beat that was partially or fully composed by the producer before any of the song’s ideas were conceived.

The methodology that we present in this section is derived from Schaefferian theory and its core typology, the TARTYP¹. The latter is a table describing sound objects in the time and frequency domains. The sound object types notated at the body of this table are defined by the intersection of the temporal and timbral characteristics specified at its margins. The time domain of the table includes two sets of terms: one describing the duration of sound objects; the other describing the formation of sound objects. The frequency domain of the table includes terminology that identifies four types of timbres.

In [11], Schaeffer provides sound recordings that exemplify each type of TARTYP sound objects, known to most theorists as the *TARTYP sound examples*. While the table does not quantify the different durations of sound objects, by examining the TARTYP sound examples we can identify a time range for each duration type (see below). Timbre and formation are much harder to quantify not only based on Schaeffer’s terminology but also based on subjective listening to his examples. In this section, we will use the timbreID tool [13, 14] to generate quantitative timbre and formation classifications of the TARTYP sound examples. We will then use the classifications derived in this fashion to analyze samples of the beat’s basic components, mapping between these components and TARTYP sound object types. Such mapping will enable us, in the following section, to use the TARTYP generative grammars [8, 9] in the analysis and re-composition of a representative hip hop drum pattern.

3.1 Hip Hop Production Paradigms

The hip hop instrumentation emerged from the rhythm and blues, funk and soul music of the late 1970s. While contemporary production of beats is often entirely computer based, production software offers virtual recreation of the acoustic, electric and electronic instrumentation of these genres. Production software templates follow arrangements of popular music with a rhythm section of drums, bass, keyboard, and guitar at the base of the arrangement, and additional instruments such as synthesizers, brass instruments, woodwind instruments, and strings, all of which are virtual instruments modeled on acoustic, electric or electronic instruments. Samples of pre-existing recordings are commonly offered as libraries of loops, or collections of sound files containing musical building blocks, such as drum patterns, chord progressions, riffs and licks, that can be repeated (i.e., looped) in different tempos and transpositions while maintain their musical integrity.

The basic components of a beat would fall in to five categories: drum simulations, bass instruments, harmonic progressions, pads, and leads. Drum simulations include drum machines and their virtual recreations, drum samples and drum loops. Bass instruments include virtual recreations of electric and acoustic basses, as well as bass and sub-bass synthesizers, and bass stations. Cyclic harmonic progressions, typical to some hip-hop sub-genres, are performed with a variety of keyboards including pianos, vintage electric pianos and organs (e.g., Fender Roads and

Hammond B3), and digital keyboards. To lesser extent, cyclic harmonic progressions are also performed with acoustic and electric guitars. Pads are sustained drones and harmonies generated by synthesizers and “strings” (i.e., electronic or virtual recreations of orchestral string sections). Leads are background or contra melodies mostly generated by synthesizers.

Beats production follows the production and postproduction practices of popular music, including multitrack recording, overdubbing, mixing and mastering. Typical multitrack recording and mixing sessions would include the individual parts of the drum kit recorded on 8 to 12 tracks, bass and keyboards each recorded on 1-2 tracks, one or more tracks of guitars, and one or more tracks of lead and backing vocals. When using drum machines and virtual instruments, the recommendation is to separate these to individual stems (see [15]). Since beats are composed without the use of notation, the DAW software workspace and timeline replace the musical score. Track labeling identifies the instrumentation. Markers on the timeline identify the sections of the songs. In many cases new timbres are generated by software or electronic instruments and are recognizable only by the track labels. At the same time, common track labels like “Synths”, “Pads” or “Leads” may say little about the timbre of the instrument and more about the function of this instrument in the arrangement.

The exploration of new timbres is part of the esthetics of beat production. Brett maintains that many producers are interested in creating a new and unique set of sounds for each song they produce [16]. Producer Bryan-Michael Cox recognizes the creation of new sounds as the main way for emerging producers to stand out in the crowded field of hip hop production [17]. Layering of multiple timbres, sometimes of the same instrument, is another beat esthetic. For example, the multitrack session of the song *Window* by Killa-L, used here as one of the sources of beat samples, includes several layers of kick drum sounds each only slightly different than the other. Another fundamental esthetic of beats is repetition. The latter may occur in almost every aspect of the arrangement from the basic patterns to a formal organization of repeated sections. Many beats will include repeated chord cycles of 2 to 4 chords, derived from jazz harmony, and used more as colors and less as functional harmony.

3.2 Beat Samples

To create a mapping between the beat’s basic components and the TARTYP sound object types, we collected samples (i.e., recorded sound objects) from a number of professionally produced hip hop songs and beats. We took the samples from the pre-mastered multitrack sessions of these songs and beats to allow access to the individual instrumental tracks. The sampled material included complete multitrack sessions of songs by hip hop artists which are available for educational and research uses through the

¹ Detailed discussion of the TARTYP and its structure, as well as a figure of the TARTYP are available in [8, 9].

Mixing Secrets Library² [18]. In addition, samples were taken from complete multitrack sessions of beats created by Houston based producer Rickey Benz as well as multitrack sessions produced by the author.

In the process of collecting samples from multitrack sessions, we followed the practices and esthetics of beat production. We identified the instruments and their function in the arrangements based on the multitrack session's track labeling and not by subjective listening to the instrument's timbre. For example, we categorized samples as pads if the track they were taken from was labeled "Pad" even if their timbre resembled the timbre of orchestral strings. The category of "Synth," therefore included a wide variety of timbres. On the other hand, the category of "Kick" was more consistent in timbre.

We determined the durations of samples based on the overall arrangement of the beat as well as the specific schemes of repetition and loops used to create the beat. The musical content of samples varied from a single note to complete phrases or chord progressions. When possible, sampling followed the editing visible in the multitrack session. For example, the samples taken from loops were the clips duplicated to create these loops. Drum samples tended to have short durations between 0.5 to 2 seconds. The drum samples included a single drum or cymbal stroke or a single gesture such as the hi hat roll known as "Trap Hat" [19] or drum fills. In contrast, the durations of samples taken from pads often exceeded 10 seconds. When possible, samples were taken from silence to silence.

The diversity of the hip hop samples in regard to timbre, duration and musical content corresponds to similar diversity displayed by the TARTYP sound examples. In the discussion of the typology of Balanced objects in [11], Schaeffer provides four sets of sound recordings that exemplified the nine Balanced sound objects. The sound sources of these recordings are specified in the example labeling as follows:

- Tracks 31-33 are labeled "instrumental"
- Tracks 34-36 are labeled "from a prepared piano"
- Tracks 37-39 are labeled "concrete"
- Tracks 40-42 are labeled "electronic"

The examples labeled "instrumental" include recordings of trumpets, piano, woodwinds and percussion, i.e., clearly identified instrumental timbres consistent with the label. The timbral identities of the examples labeled "concrete" and "electronic" are much less clear. Within the "concrete" examples one can identify both electronically generated sound (the impulse and iterative) and processed violin and piano sounds (sustain). While the "electronic" examples are all electronically generated they display a variety of timbres. Hence, Schaeffer's use of labels such as "concrete" and "electronic" is similar to the hip hop producers' use of the labels "Synth" and "Pad" where the label is derived from the sound generation method or the musical function but say very little about the timbre.

Schaeffer, in these sound examples, demonstrates the diverse possible manifestations of the sound object as an "event perceived as a whole, a coherent entity" [10]. The

variety of timbres, temporal organizations and in particular musical content displayed by these examples demonstrates the sound object as such (a coherent entity), whether it is a single note or a fully composed orchestral passage. Similarly, in the sampling of beat material we aimed to reveal the sound objects within the instrumental tracks of the hip hop song. Therefore, the beat samples display similar diversity. Neither Schaeffer's examples nor the beat samples aim to demonstrate an individual timbral characteristic or an individual temporal characteristic. Nonetheless the identification of sound object types based on the TARTYP is done by intersecting the temporal and timbral characteristics specified at the margins of this table. And therefore, to identify the sound object type of each beat sample we must analyze its temporal and timbral characteristics.

3.3 Quantitative Analysis and Classification

The quantitative analysis we present in this section is focused on measurable characteristics of TARTYP sound objects. Framed within machine learning paradigms, the analysis considers Schaeffer's examples as training datasets and the beat samples as testing datasets. Since the TARTYP includes only descriptive terms of sound objects characteristics, the measurement system we have used in this analysis was derived from the TARTYP sound examples. As mentioned above, the identification of TARTYP sound object types is done by intersecting temporal and timbral characteristics. Each of the sound object types is therefore defined in our analysis by two sets of measurements extracted from the TARTYP examples. By applying the same system to the beat samples and comparing their measurements with those of the TARTYP examples, we can associate beat samples with sound object types.

Within the time domain, the TARTYP applies two sets of descriptors: one for duration and the other for formation (*facture*)³. Duration is described by the terms that appear at the top of the table: *short duration*, *micro-objects*; *moderate duration*, *temporal unity*; and *long duration* (*macro-objects*) of *no temporal unity*. Formation (*facture*) is described by five terms appearing below the duration terminology: *impulse*; *formed iteration*; *formed sustain*; *non-existent facture*; and *unpredictable facture*. The duration terminology clearly identifies three types of durations: short, moderate and long. The formation (*facture*) terminology is much less clear. However, additional notation at the bottom of the TARTYP provides more clarification. This notation divides the table into *iterative sounds* (the three right columns) and *held sounds* (the three left columns), leaving out the column with the header *impulse* at the center of the table.

It is clear from this TARTYP terminology that sustain and iteration are fundamental elements when defining formations. The latter can be described also as amplitude envelopes where a sustain sound includes a single attack and iterative sound includes multiple attacks. The Schaefferian approach to iteration is explained by Chion in [10]:

² The artists and songs are as follows: Killa-L, 'Window'; Little Chicago's Finest, 'My Own'; M.E.R.C. Music, 'Knockout'; Ryan Cali, 'Back Down', 'Crazy'

³ The terms *form* and *facture* are discussed in [10]. Nonetheless the term *facture* is subject to much semantic debate among Schaefferian scholars.

The name iterative is given to sounds whose sustainment is prolonged by iteration, i.e., by repetition of impulses at close intervals.

He also maintains the following in [10]:

Conversely, if the iteration is too spaced out, the iterative sound is no longer perceived as a unit, and each impulse once again becomes an isolated sound object.

Therefore, in our analysis we considered a drum pattern not as a formed iterative sound object but as a combination of impulse sound objects. On the other hand, we considered the trap hat gesture [19], being a series of attacks in very close time intervals, as a formed iterative object. Another example of formed iteration are sounds generated by granular synthesis.

Duration is easily measured in seconds and milliseconds. To define a time range for each one of the three duration types we measured the durations of the TARTYP sound objects associated with this type. Specifically, the sound examples of short duration objects are 1 second or less; the sound examples of medium duration objects are 1-10 seconds; and the sound examples of long duration objects are 10 seconds or more. We then divided the beat samples into three sets, each of which is associated with one of the TARTYP duration types, based on the samples' measured durations.

In measuring formation (*facture*), we focused on identifying the attacks occurring throughout the duration of the sound. Attack detection is done by the bark~ object included in the timbreID tool kit we have used for timbral analysis (see below). The bark~ object is used to trigger spectral analysis and assignment of timbre IDs within timbreID patch [13]. A sound object including a single attack will be assigned one timbre ID. A sound object including multiple attacks, will receive multiple timbre IDs. The use of the timbreID patch for strictly timbre identification as demonstrated in [13] considers only single attack sounds. However, since we are analyzing two dimensional TARTYP sound objects, some of which characterized by *formed iteration*, we must consider multi-attack sound objects. Using attack detection within the timbre identification process allows us to bridge between formation (*facture*) and timbre, characteristics separated in the TARTYP to two different domains. With the timbreID patch, sound object examples and hip hop samples receiving similar timbre IDs will also have a similar formation (*facture*).

We elected to use the machine learning tool timbreID within the Pure Data environment [13, 14] for analysis and measurement of sound objects characteristics in the frequency domain. This tool defines a classification of timbres based on sets of features taken from audio recordings used as the training set. The tool creates a database of timbres in which each timbre receives an ID number. Consequently, the database can be used to identify these timbres in audio recordings used as the testing set. The training set in our analysis was the collection of TARTYP sound examples. The testing set was the collection of samples of the beat's basic components taken from the multitrack recording sessions of hip hop songs, i.e., the beat samples. The goal of this analysis was to point out similarities in timbre between the TARTYP sound examples and beat samples.

Since, as mentioned above, attack detection is incorporated within the timbreID patch, the process of timbre

identification is affected by the duration of the audio recording, i.e., the timbreID patch tends to define more timbres in longer audio recordings. To increase the accuracy and effectiveness of the classification, we divided the training set into two subsets, one of short and medium durations and the other of long durations. In the TARTYP, the sub-collection of short and medium durations at the center of the table includes 12 sound object types: 9 Balanced, and 3 Excentric (see [8, 9]). In [11], Schaeffer provides about three sound examples for each sound object type. Hence, the training set of short and medium duration included 35 audio files from Schaeffer's sound object examples. While similar analysis was conducted also in regard to sound objects of long durations the discussion here will focus on the short and medium durations subset.

Sound Object/ Formation	Num. of Examples	Avg. Duration (seconds)	Timbre ID range	Avg. Attack Detections
N (sus)	2	6.5	18-20	1.5
X (sus)	3	5.6	67-76	3.3
Y (sus)	3	5	90-96	2.3
W (sus)	4	6	28-48	5.25
N' (imp)	3	2	15-17	1
X' (imp)	3	2.3	64-66	1
Y' (imp)	3	2	87-89	1
Φ (imp)	2	2	21-27	3.5
N'' (iter)	3	4.3	6-14	3
X'' (iter)	3	4.6	49-63	5
Y'' (iter)	3	4.3	77-86	3.3
K (iter)	3	1	0-5	2

Table 1. Timbre IDs associated with each sound object in the database of 96 timbres yield by BFCC analysis (sus = formed sustain; imp = impulse; iter = formed iteration).

The analysis of the short and medium duration training subset was done with 25 features of Bark-frequency cepstrum (BFCC) generated by the bfcc~ object from the timbreID tool kit. The BFCC analysis of the short and medium duration subset yielded a database of 96 timbre IDs. Based on this analysis, each TARTYP sound object type was associated with a range of timbres within the database. Table 1 shows the timbre IDs associated with each sound object in the database of 96 timbres provided by the BFCC analysis. This table also specifies the number of examples used for each sound object type, the average duration of these examples and the average number of attacks detected in these examples. The latter are measurements describing the sound objects' formations which are specified in parenthesis together with the sound object notation.

The training set database was used to identify timbre similarities between the TARTYP sound objects and the beat samples. These samples were categorized based on the labeling of the tracks they originated from and the function of these tracks in the arrangement of the song. The categories of beat samples were: Kick, Snare, Clap, Hi-Hat, Cymbal, Bass, Pads, Synth, and SynthFX. These samples were marked as having either short and medium durations (between 0 to 10 seconds), or having long durations (more than 10 seconds). All sample categories included samples of short and medium duration, although only some categories included samples of long duration. This can be explained by musical functionality and content. For

example, there were no long duration samples in the categories of Kick and Snare, since, in accordance with the TARTYP approach to iteration mention above, these samples included single drum strokes and therefore are generally very short. Long durations appeared only in categories such as Bass, Pads and Synth, as these include sustained harmonies and drones. Table 2 specifies the beat sample categories, the number of samples in each category, and the breakdown by short/medium duration vs long duration.

Category	Total No. of Samples	Short/Medium Duration Samples	Long Duration Samples
Kick	15	15	0
Snare	10	10	0
Clap	6	6	0
Hi Hat	11	11	0
Cymbal	11	11	0
Bass	9	7	2
Pads	12	5	7
Synth	16	15	1
SynthFX	5	5	0

Table 2. Beat samples

The analysis of beat samples was done in categories. Like the discussion of the training set, the discussion here will focus on samples of short and medium duration. The samples of each category were tested against the BFCC database, yielding varying numbers of timbre IDs associated with the category. The testing results provided a list of timbre IDs that were recognized within the category and the number of times each timbre ID was recognized. The testing results also showed the number of attack detections by the bark~ object for each sample and the average of detections for the category. From a TARTYP perspective, the most commonly occurring timbre ID and average number of attack detections define the timbre and formation of the beat sample category. This information can be compared with the range of timbre IDs and number of attack detections defined by the training database for each sound object and in turn point to associations between beat sample categories and TARTYP sound objects.

For example, the kick category included 15 samples. The average attack detection for this category was 1.13 attacks per sample. The timbre IDs recognized in this category were: 21 (twice), 22 (twice), 35 (once), 37 (once), 38 (twice), 39 (once), 90 (twice), 92 (three times) and 96 (three times). Hence 8 timbre ID occurrences were in the range of the Y sound object (90, 92, 96); 5 timbre ID occurrences were in the range of the W sound object (35, 37, 38, 39); and 4 timbre ID occurrences were in the range of the Φ sound object (21, 22). Based on these timber IDs, the Kick category showed 47% timbral similarity with Y, 29.5 % timbral similarity with W, and 23% timbral similarity with Φ . In regard to formation the average attack detection for the Y sound object is 2.3, the W sound object is 5.25, and for the Φ sound object is 3.5. In addition, out of the three sound examples of the Y object, two examples had only one attack detected while third example had five attacks detected. Hence based on these similarities in duration, formation and timbre the Kick category of hip hop samples can be associated with to the Y sound object. Table 3 specifies attack detections and timbre IDs recognized in the drum-kit categories (Kick, Snare, Clap, Hi hat, and

Cymbal) out of the short and medium duration beat samples and their association with sound objects. Table 4 presents the association of short and medium duration beat sample categories with sound objects.

Category	Avg-Attack Detections	Timbre IDs	Primary Sound Objects	Secondary Sound Objects
Kick	1.13	21, 22, 35, 37, 38, 39, 90, 92, 96	Y (47%)	W (29.5%), Φ (23.5%)
Snare	2.6	18, 36, 39, 44, 64, 65	N (58%)	W (23%) X' (19%)
Clap	1	18, 39, 90	N (50%)	Y (33%) W (17%)
Hi Hat	1.18	65, 34	X' (92%)	W (8%)
Cymbal	1.33	18, 34, 65, 76	N (41%) X' (41%)	X (8%) W (8%)

Table 3. Attack detections, timbre IDs and sound object associations in the drum-kit categories

Category	Primary Sound Objects	Secondary Sound Object
Kick	Y (47%)	W (29.5%), Φ (23.5%)
Snare	N (58%)	W (23%), X' (19%)
Clap	N (50%)	Y (33%), W (17%)
Hi Hat	X' (92%)	W (8%)
Cymbal	N (41%), X' (41%)	X (8%), W (8%)
Bass	Y (94%)	W: (4%), Φ : (2%)
Pads	X (39%), Y'' (21%)	X' (10.5%), Φ (10.5%) N (5.5%), K (5.5%) W (5.5%), X'' (2.5%)
Synth	W (37.5%), N (25%)	K (12.5%), X (6.25%) Y (6.25%), X' (3.125%) X'' (3.125%), Y'' (3.125%) Φ (3.125%)
SynthFX	Y (50%), Y' (24%)	Φ (13.5%), N (6.5%) W (4%), X'' (2%)

Table 4. Associations of beat sample categories with sound objects

4. GENERATIVE GRAMMARS

The results presented in Table 3 and Table 4 show the strong association of the drum-kit categories to three TARTYP sound objects N, Y and X'. These sound objects are members of the Balanced subcollection of the TARTYP [8, 9, 10]. The TARTYP generative grammars, presented in [8] and [9], include grammar definitions for each TARTYP sub-collection and detailed demonstration of rewrite rules in the Balanced subcollection grammar. In this section we will use this grammar to describe and re-compose a typical drum pattern which is commonly used in hip hop beats, demonstrating the potential application of the TARTYP generative grammars for beat analysis.

The Balanced generative grammar as presented in [8, 9] includes six terminal symbols, each of which represent a sound object characteristic either in the time or frequency domain of the TARTYP. As such, each terminal symbol is equivalent to a subset of the Balanced object subcollection. Furthermore, each sound object, based on its characteristics, is described by two terminal symbols, one from the time domain and one from frequency domain. Using the association of the drum-kit categories with sound objects presented in Table 4, we can map these categories to terminal symbols, and consequently each category would be

described by two terminal symbols. Equations (1.1) through (1.6) specify the Balanced grammar terminal symbols, their equivalent sound object subsets, and the mapping to drum-kit categories.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DEFINITE} &= \{[N | N' | N'']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Snare} | \text{Clap} | \text{Cymbal} \} & (1.1) \\ \text{COMPLEX} &= \{[X | X' | X'']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Cymbal} | \text{Hi Hat} \} & (1.2) \\ \text{VARIABLE} &= \{[Y | Y' | Y'']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Kick} \} & (1.3) \\ \text{IMPULSE} &= \{[N' | X' | Y']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Cymbal} | \text{Hi Hat} \} & (1.4) \\ \text{FORMED ITER} &= \{[N'' | X'' | Y'']+\} & (1.5) \\ \text{FORMED SUS} &= \{[N | X | Y]+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Snare} | \text{Clap} | \text{Cymbal} | \text{Kick} \} & (1.6) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1 presents a basic drum pattern that is commonly used in hip hop beats [20]. This pattern utilizes only three drum-kit categories: Kick, Snare and Hi Hat. Equations (2.1) through (2.6) specify the mapping of these three categories to the terminal symbols of the Balanced grammar.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DEFINITE} &= \{[N | N' | N'']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Snare} \} & (2.1) \\ \text{COMPLEX} &= \{[X | X' | X'']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Hi Hat} \} & (2.2) \\ \text{VARIABLE} &= \{[Y | Y' | Y'']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{kick} \} & (2.3) \\ \text{IMPULSE} &= \{[N' | X' | Y']+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Hi Hat} \} & (2.4) \\ \text{FORMED ITER} &= \{[N'' | X'' | Y'']+\} & (2.5) \\ \text{FORMED SUS} &= \{[N | X | Y]+\} \leftarrow \{ \text{Snare} | \text{kick} \} & (2.6) \end{aligned}$$

Alternatively, equations (3.1) through (3.3) specify the two terminal symbols describing each one of the drum-kit categories included in the drum pattern of Figure 1.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Kick} &= \text{FORMED SUS} + \text{VARIABLE} & (3.1) \\ \text{Snare} &= \text{FORMED SUS} + \text{DEFINITE} & (3.2) \\ \text{Hi Hat} &= \text{IMPULSE} + \text{COMPLEX} & (3.3) \end{aligned}$$

Based on the Balanced grammar definition from [8, 9] and the relationships specified in equations (2.1) through (2.6) as well equations (3.1) through (3.3) we can now define legal sets of rewrite rules within the Balanced grammar that can in turn generate rewrite paths describing drum patterns including a kick, snare and hi hat, such as the one shown in figure 1. Equations (4.1) through (4.14) present such a rule set with the start symbol balanced:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{balanced} &\rightarrow \text{FORMED SUS bal_expre_v} & (4.1) \\ \text{balanced} &\rightarrow \text{IMPULSE bal_expre_c} & (4.2) \\ \text{bal_expre_v} &\rightarrow \text{VARIABLE FORMED_SUS} & (4.3) \\ \text{bal_expre_v} &\rightarrow \text{VARIABLE FORMED_SUS bal_expre_i} & (4.4) \\ \text{bal_expre_v} &\rightarrow \text{VARIABLE FORMED_SUS bal_expre_fs} & (4.5) \\ \text{bal_expre_i} &\rightarrow \text{IMPULSE bal_expre_c} & (4.6) \\ \text{bal_expre_c} &\rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE} & (4.7) \\ \text{bal_expre_c} &\rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE bal_expre_fs} & (4.8) \\ \text{bal_expre_fs} &\rightarrow \text{FORMED_SUS bal_expre_d} & (4.9) \\ \text{bal_expre_fs} &\rightarrow \text{FORMED_SUS bal_expre_v} & (4.10) \\ \text{bal_expre_d} &\rightarrow \text{DEFINITE FORMED_SUS} & (4.11) \\ \text{bal_expre_d} &\rightarrow \text{DEFINITE FORMED_SUS bal_expre_fs} & (4.12) \\ \text{bal_expre_d} &\rightarrow \text{DEFINITE FORMED_SUS bal_expre_i} & (4.13) \\ \text{bal_expre_c} &\rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE bal_expre_i} & (4.14) \end{aligned}$$

This rule set is legal within the Balanced grammar since it contains two rules with start head balanced, it contains no duplicate rules, and all non-terminal symbols that appear in the body of a rule have at least one other corresponding rule where they appear only in the head. This rule set is useful for describing the drum pattern since all terminating rules include a pair of terminal symbols matching one of the drum-kit categories as specified in equations (3.1) through (3.3). In addition, the set includes non-terminating rules with pairs of terminal symbols matching the three drum-kit categories discussed. Therefore, a path generated in this rule set will include one or more pairs of terminal

symbols matching one or more of the three drum-kit categories.

The path presented in equation (5) was generated by the rule set of equations (4.1) through (4.14).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Path: } &\rightarrow \text{R:4.1} \rightarrow \text{FORMED_SUS} \rightarrow \text{R:4.4} \rightarrow \text{VARIABLE} \\ &\text{FORMED_SUS (= Kick)} \rightarrow \text{R:4.6} \rightarrow \text{IMPULSE} \rightarrow \text{R:4.14} \\ &\rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE (= Hi Hat)} \rightarrow \text{R:4.6} \rightarrow \text{IMPULSE} \\ &\rightarrow \text{R:4.8} \rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE (= Hi Hat)} \rightarrow \text{R:4.10} \rightarrow \\ &\text{FORMED_SUS} \rightarrow \text{R:4.13} \rightarrow \text{DEFINITE FORMED_SUS (= snare)} \\ &\rightarrow \text{R:4.6} \rightarrow \text{IMPULSE} \rightarrow \text{R:4.14} \rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE (= Hi Hat)} \\ &\rightarrow \text{R:4.6} \rightarrow \text{IMPULSE} \rightarrow \text{R:4.7} \rightarrow \text{COMPLEX IMPULSE (= Hi Hat)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

It describes the first two beats of the pattern in figure 1 including the first kick strike, the first two hi hat strikes, the first snare strike, and the third and fourth hi hat strikes. The regeneration of these two beats using the path of equation (5) is described in figure 2.

Figure 1. Basic hip hop drum pattern

Figure 2. Regeneration of the first two beats of the pattern in figure 1 using the path of equation (5).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The clear association between the drum-kit categories and the Balanced sound objects, as presented in tables 3 and 4 enabled us to use the TARTYP generative grammars in the description of a basic drum pattern. At the same time, our classification of other beat sample categories have shown much less decisive association with TARTYP sound objects. This can be explained by the diversified makeup of these categories as opposed to the more uniform makeup of the drum-kit categories. For example, the Pads category is defined by the function of the track within the arrangement and may include a variety of timbres from orchestral strings to unidentified Sci-Fi sounds. This is in contrast with the drum-kit categories in which sounds more closely resemble the acoustic instrument.

In future research we suggest using the methods demonstrated in this paper in the analysis of beats produced by the same producer. As noted by [3] and [17] hip-hop producers tend to develop their sound identity based on the selection of instruments, samples and sounds they use in

the production of their beats. Therefore, a classification of beat samples taken from multiple beats produced by the same producer is likely to yield more decisive association of all sample categories with TARTYP sound objects. This in turn will allow us to use rewrite rules in the TARTYP generative grammars for analysis and re-composition of the complete beat arrangement.

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